

QR Code Attendance System

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays the use of smartphones can make everyone's life simple and easy. In line with the technological advances, this paper proposed smartphones based QR codes to record the presence staff of Electrical Engineering Department. The proposed system used QR code to identify individuals working in the department and smartphone as a QR code mobile scanner. Each staff card of Electrical Engineering Department will be equipped with a unique QR code. The interface of QR code mobile application scanner designed based on a real-time scanner using MIT Apps Inventor software. The integration of Google Apps Script applications and the Android Barcode Scanner enables mobile application scanners function as real scanners and work well with the database. The QR code mobile application scanner has two main buttons: The In Time button to record start-up working time and the Out Time button to record time out of office. Employees need to press the In Time or Out Time buttons before scanning the QR code to the scanner. The system automatically verifies the QR code with the data in the database. If the data is match, it will automatically record the time In or time Out of staff in the system and appear to the scanner screen. The developed QR Code Attendance System is very practical as its portable scanners and database systems are also accessible online by management. An accurate report based on the staff attendance also can generated quickly by using Google Sheets. Therefore, the staff attendance monitoring system will be more effective and easier to control.

Introduction

There are many methods of recording an attendance in the market such using punch cards, fingerprint systems, barcodes and also RFID. Each method has it's advantages and reasons why it's choose by the management. Polytechnic Ibrahim sultan has been using fingerprints since 2014 for monitoring staff attendance system. However, there was a malfunction of the fingerprints scanner at the Electrical Engineering Department. This caused staff difficulties as they had to scan their fingerprints elsewhere. Based on the problem, the author come up with the good solution by using smartphone-based attendance system. There are many examples of attendance systems in the market that use smartphones such as QR Code Attendance System. This feature lets us take record of employee attendance with just a tap of QR code to mobile application scanner (Wei.X et al. , 2017). QR Code Attendance System is simple and convenient to use, no external devices like Biometric Scanners are required. Everything is done on our smartphones.

A few studies were conducted on the use of QR code for attendance systems. QR code is being displayed for students during or at the beginning of each lecture and student need to scan the QR code using their smartphone for confirming their presence at class (Masalha.F & Hirzallah.N ,2014). The system proposed by Abdelhafez. H et al. (2019) uses the QR code as the subject register. There is different QR code for each course or subject that the students should take in the semester. Each faculty member gives students a QR code to scan for evidence of attendance at each

learning session. The propose system developed using Android studio, PHP to connect with MySQL database, XAMPP, and Java SE Development Kit (JDK). Wei. X et al. (2017) successfully develop the applications for generating the QR Code by entering the student details and for taking the attendance lecturer need to scan the QR code of the student in order to confirm their attendance. This system used Smartphone running in Android OS, SQLite Database and Android Studio.

After reviewing previous studies, the author developed QR Attendance System for Electrical Engineering Department by using QR code, Android OS mobile scanner module and Google Sheets as a database for this system. This proposed project is a combination of android applications developed for taking and storing the attendance staff on the daily basis working day. The mobile module enables staff to scan QR code to confirm their attendance. The request is then sent to backend service module for verification. Once the attendance is verified, the backend service module will update the database on attendance records.

The advantages of using QR Code Attendance System are provide an efficient and automated method to track attendance for staff using QR Code. The system is easy to maintain and very cost-effective as it reduces paper usage (Wei. X et al. ,2017). This system can also be used for recording the attendance of staff for other purposes such as attendance of meetings, seminars and others.

Methodology

To achieve the project objectives, a step-by-step methodology has been followed. The details of methodology are given below:

- Develop a QR code generator android app using the details of staff ID
- Develop a Mobile Scanner Modules for scanning the QR code.
- Develop the database using Google Sheets for recording attendance

A QR code is a two-dimensional code used to record thousands of characters and numbers in a small image (Android QR Code Scanner, 2016). The proposed system used monkey QR code generator to generate QR code for each staff of Electrical Engineering Department. The QR Code is the main component which will be put into database and will be print out to the staff ID card. Mobile module scanner for this proposed system running in Android OS for record attendance by scanning QR Code. To develop the mobile apps scanner interface, the author use MIT Inventor and the integration of Android Barcode Scanner. While Google Apps Script is used for scripting mobile scanner apps to the database. The system will able to verify staffs' identity using QR code given on each staff and recorded to the system instantly.

Google Sheets are used for storing the staff data such as staff ID, name, In time, Out time, time of working hours, overtimes and less time. The developed database contains all the information of staff attendance on daily basis as shown in Figure 1. By using the proposed system, the admin can monitor the attendance records by daily to monthly record for each staff and issue notification if staff's attendance lower than working hours' time.

The flow chart on Figure 2 shows how the project that has been developed works. Each staff of Electrical Engineering Department are given QR Code on their staff card. Sample of ID card design equip with QR code shown on Figure 3. For record the staff attendance, staff need to scan the QR Code to the mobile apps' scanner. The result will appear on mobile apps' screen as shown on Figure 2 and instantly recorded to database. The data will not be recorded to the system if QR code does not match.

SISTEM E-KEHADIRAN JABATAN KEJURUTERAAN ELEKTRIK								
TARIKH:	9 MAC 2020							
HARI:	ISNIN							
Id	Name	In Time	Out Time	Working Hours	Regular	Overtime	Lesstime	Remark
2sd12cs001	EN. MAZLAN BIN KARIM @ HUSSEIN	8:00:00	17:45:51	9:45:51	9:00:00	0:45:51	0	
2sd12cs002	PN. ANIZAH BT. HASSAN	7:30:58	16:55:30	9:24:32	9:00:00	0:24:32	0	
2sd12cs003	EN. MOHD FAIRUZ BIN SALLEH	8:05:00	17:30:20	9:25:20	9:00:00	0:25:20	0	
2sd12cs004	PN. ROSSIELYANA BINTI ABDUL RAHIM	6:27:00	17:00:00	10:33:00	9:00:00	1:33:00	0	
2sd12cs005	EN. AIDI BIN SULAIMAN	8:00:13	17:10:00	9:09:47	9:00:00	0:09:47	0	
2sd12cs006	PN. NORLI BT. JASWADI	7:40:00	17:00:00	9:20:00	9:00:00	0:20:00	0	
2sd12cs007	EN. SARAWANAN A/L LETCHUMANAN	8:00:11	17:04:00	9:03:49	9:00:00	0:03:49	0	
2sd12cs008	PN. SITI NORAIDAH BT. SAIF	8:00:00	17:30:00	9:30:00	9:00:00	0:30:00	0	
2sd12cs009	PN. ZUBYDAH BT. MUSTAFA	7:50:00	17:00:00	9:10:00	9:00:00	0:10:00	0	
2sd12cs010	PN. NORMAH BT. SAPUAN	7:50:00	17:00:00	9:10:00	9:00:00	0:10:00	0	
2sd12cs011	TN. HJ. ISHAK BIN TAMAN	7:51:00	17:00:00	9:09:00	9:00:00	0:09:00	0	
2sd12cs012	Y.M TENGKU NADZION BIN TENGKU IBRAHIM	8:14:00	17:00:00	8:46:00	9:00:00	0	0:14:00	
2sd12cs013	EN. NOR HAZAT BIN OMAR	8:00:01	17:00:00	8:59:59	9:00:00	0	0:00:01	
2sd12cs014	CIK ALINAH BT. SARING	7:50:00	16:30:00	8:40:00	9:00:00	0	0:20:00	
2sd12cs015	PN. JAMALIAH BT. JAMIAN	8:00:10	17:10:00	9:09:50	9:00:00	0:09:50	0	

Figure 1:QR Code Attendance System Database

Figure 2 : The Flowchart of developed system

Result and discussion

The application used for developing this project are Google Sheets, Google Apps Script, MIT App Inventor and QR code generator. Google Sheets is a spreadsheet program included as part of a free web-based software office suite offered by Google service. Next application is Google Apps Script which is use for scripting the platform of QR code mobile apps. The author chooses to use this application because all this application is free to use, and it's really helped the author to develop this project.

After many trial using the application, the author successfully set up the mobile module interface and integrated it with the database. Figure 3 show the process of using QR Code Attendance System. The QR code attendance system will record the staff In Time and Out Time instantly after scanning their QR code using mobile apps' that act as a QR code scanner. On the

apps interface showing of two button which has different usage. First button is In Time, which is used to record the time of staff coming in for start working. While the second button is Out Time, which is use to record time out of staff attendance. Staff need to press In Time button or Out Time button before scanning their QR code. Less than three seconds after scanning the QR code, it's instantly recorded into the database and the mobile module screen will show "Thank You, your in time is". For Out time, the mobile module screen will show "Thank You, your out time is". The responses appears on the mobile attendance screen as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3 :Process of using QR Code Attendance System

The database of this QR Code Attendance System contain the information such as Table 1.

Item	Descriptions
Staff ID	The staff information containing Name and No ID.
In Time	Time of staff come to the office for working.
Out Time	Time of staff out from the office
Working Hours	The designated working hours are 9 hours a day including breaks from 1.00 pm to 2.00 pm.
Overtime	Staff working period over time of working hours (overtime). The cell colour will turn green if staff working hours overtime.
Less Time	Staff working period less than time of working hours. The cell colour will turn red if staff working hours less then 9 hours.
Remark	Records need to be filled out by monitoring attendance in charge if staff working periods are less than working hours by referring related document such as staff outstation form and record out of office permission.

Staff Attendance monitoring system is very important for management to monitor and evaluate of staff discipline in time management. The proposed project database are stored in the cloud for easy access by the management. The database also automatically calculates the total time of overtime and less time working hours. Therefore, it's easier for management to monitor staff attendance especially for less working hours. The management may notify the affected employees and take other actions such as notify them for taking a day off.

The author faced many problems during preparing this project. Even though this project is difficult to accomplish, it's finally done successfully. Some problem that has been made are come from author's mistake in technical part such as coding error. Next problem is when the interface of mobile apps not working properly which is can't integrate with the Google Sheets as a database. The authors tried so hard to find the solution and finally successfully solve the problem by guideline from MIT app inventor and Google Script forum.

Lastly, is block apps error. This is the most complicated errors because block apps are connected to each other in many parts of block apps. To find the solution author needs to troubleshoot the block apps one by one and found some minor problem in time application. After doing some troubleshooting, the system developed finally works as the author goal.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this project has been successfully introduced for use in Electrical Engineering Department. The proposed project is adaptable option because does not require additional devices as a scanner. The system only requires smartphones and internet accessibility to operate. The staff attendance status will be appearing to the mobile apps screen and store to the database. The database of attendance record can show daily record working days and the compilation of a month of working attendance.

The next possible proposal for future improvement of proposed project is to suggest the management of Polytechnic Ibrahim Sultan to add QR code for whole staff and student ID cards. This improvement is certainly possible to maximize the benefits of project that has been develop. QR code attendance systems can also be applied as a method of recording attendance during meetings, courses, monthly assemblies and more.

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